

- IEEE

String: ("All Metadata":"health system" OR "All Metadata":"health systems" OR "All Metadata":"sistema de saúde" OR "All Metadata":"sistemas de saúde" OR "All Metadata":"sistema de salud" OR "All Metadata":"sistemas de salud") AND ("All Metadata":"framework" OR "All Metadata":"process" OR "All Metadata":"method" OR "All Metadata":"model" OR "All Metadata":"technique" OR "All Metadata":"tool" OR "All Metadata":"standard" OR "All Metadata":"pattern" OR "All Metadata":"processo" OR "All Metadata":"método" OR "All Metadata":"modelo" OR "All Metadata":"técnica" OR "All Metadata":"ferramenta" OR "All Metadata":"padrão" OR "All Metadata":"proceso" OR "All Metadata":"herramienta" OR "All Metadata":"estándar") AND ("All Metadata":"open source" OR "All Metadata":"código aberto" OR "All Metadata":"código abierto")

Link:

[https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/search/searchresult.jsp?action=search&newsearch=true&matchBoolean=true&queryText=\(%22All%20Metadata%22:%22health%20system%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22health%20systems%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistema%20de%20sa%C3%BAde%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistemas%20de%20sa%C3%BAde%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistema%20de%20salud%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistemas%20de%20salud%22\)%20AND%20\(%22All%20Metadata%22:process%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:framework%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:method%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:model%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:technique%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:tool%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:standard%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:pattern%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:processo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:m%C3%A9todo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:modelo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:t%C3%A9cnica%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:ferramenta%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:padr%C3%A3o%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:proceso%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:herramienta%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:est%C3%A1ndar\)%20AND%20\(%22All%20Metadata%22:development%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:implementation%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:desenvolvimento%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:implementa%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:desarrollo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:implementaci%C3%B3n\)%20AND%20\(%22All%20Metadata%22:%22open%20source%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22c%C3%B3digo%20aberto%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22c%C3%B3digo%20abierto%22\)](https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/search/searchresult.jsp?action=search&newsearch=true&matchBoolean=true&queryText=(%22All%20Metadata%22:%22health%20system%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22health%20systems%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistema%20de%20sa%C3%BAde%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistemas%20de%20sa%C3%BAde%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistema%20de%20salud%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22sistemas%20de%20salud%22)%20AND%20(%22All%20Metadata%22:process%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:framework%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:method%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:model%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:technique%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:tool%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:standard%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:pattern%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:processo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:m%C3%A9todo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:modelo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:t%C3%A9cnica%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:ferramenta%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:padr%C3%A3o%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:proceso%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:herramienta%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:est%C3%A1ndar)%20AND%20(%22All%20Metadata%22:development%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:implementation%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:desenvolvimento%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:implementa%C3%A7%C3%A3o%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:desarrollo%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:implementaci%C3%B3n)%20AND%20(%22All%20Metadata%22:%22open%20source%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22c%C3%B3digo%20aberto%22%20OR%20%22All%20Metadata%22:%22c%C3%B3digo%20abierto%22))

- ACM

String: [[All: "health system"] OR [All: "health systems"] OR [All: "sistema de saúde"] OR [All: "sistemas de saúde"] OR [All: "sistema de salud"] OR [All: "sistemas de salud"]] AND [[All: process] OR [All: framework] OR [All: method] OR [All: model] OR [All: technique] OR [All: tool] OR [All: standard] OR [All: pattern] OR [All: processo] OR [All: método] OR [All: modelo] OR [All: técnica] OR [All: ferramenta] OR [All: padrão] OR [All: proceso] OR [All: herramienta] OR [All: estándar]] AND [[All: development] OR [All: implementation] OR [All: desenvolvimento] OR [All: implementação] OR [All: desarrollo] OR [All: implementación]] AND [[All: "open source"] OR [All: "código aberto"] OR [All: "código abierto"]]

Link:

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- **Pubmed**

String: (("health system" OR "health systems" OR "sistema de saúde" OR "sistemas de saúde" OR "sistema de salud" OR "sistemas de salud") AND (process OR framework OR method OR model OR technique OR tool OR standard OR pattern OR processo OR método OR modelo OR técnica OR ferramenta OR padrão OR proceso OR herramienta OR estándar) AND (development OR implementation OR desenvolvimento OR implementação OR desarrollo OR implementación) AND ("open source" OR "código aberto" OR "código abierto"))

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- **Scopus**

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Link:

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